

Report “Lattice structures in 3D printing: design and FEA analysis”

Institution: Friuli Innovazione Scarl [TEC4I FVG]

Author: Luigi Valan

Lattice structures are repeating patterns that, when connected, form three dimensional shapes.

Well-designed lattices can make parts lighter and stronger, absorb impact more efficiently, and be better customized to their end-use. Understanding how to use and create these structures is an essential part of product engineering and industrial design in 3D printing for prototypes and production parts.

They have some unique properties that can be extremely useful when designing a part or product, which are near impossible to replicate with conventional manufacturing methods. It's possible applying lattice structures with any type of 3D printing and nearly any material.

Using a lattice in design can drastically reduce the amount of material that is used by removing most of the material in non-critical areas. If the part is being manufactured using powder or resin-based 3D printing processes, this can result in a big cost saving.

The reduction of material used has another benefit also – weight savings. In many applications, the final assembled mass of the part or assembly is a tightly constrained objective, and lighter is usually better. Depending on the lattice type chosen, weight savings can be very significant, and this has many advantages, from reduced fuel use in automotive applications to improved patient recovery time in medical cases.

Lattice structures have many properties that are advantageous for absorbing energy. By varying the density and even cell type in different areas, a design can be made to absorb energy effectively in different directions. Compared to standard foam used in a wide range of products, complex lattice structures can redirect and better distribute energy in multiple directions to absorb impact forces, all while taking advantage of the various properties of modern additive manufacturing resins.

The surface area of a lattice is many times greater than that of a solid component of the same size. This can be hugely useful for applications involving heat exchange or chemical catalysis that rely on high surface areas to achieve their function.

Without considering the mechanical and physical characteristics, these structures have a pleasant aesthetic impact and therefore can also be used simply to improve the aesthetics of a product or component.

The main areas of application of lattice structures include:

- Aerospace
- Automotive
- Medical
- Sports Equipment

- Heat Exchangers
- Consumer Products

There are several types of lattice structure all based upon a unit cell. This is the repeating unit that is copied repeatedly in multiple directions to make the structure as a whole:

- **Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS)** lattices are created when a trigonometric equation is used to generate the unit cell. The 'gyroid' TPMS cell, for example, is made up of all the points inside the cell for which the following equation holds true:

- $\sin(x)\cos(y) + \sin(y)\cos(z) + \sin(z)\cos(x)=0$

Different but similar equations like this produce the different TPMS lattice types.

- **Strut lattices (or beam lattices)** are made up of interconnected beams, joined in various patterns as defined by the unit cell. The struts can be joined by the vertices of the cubic cell, the edges, and the faces, and different combinations of these connection points produce the different types.
- **Planar lattices** are created when a 2D unit cell is extruded in 3D. The most common type of planar lattice is a honeycomb structure.

Each of these types of lattices can also be made from a periodic lattice into a stochastic lattice by varying its parameters randomly in different directions. This can have advantages in some applications by giving the structure similar properties in every direction (making it isotropic).

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is a powerful tool for investigating the mechanical response of complex structures, providing valuable insights into the behaviour under different loading conditions. This tool enables the prediction and optimization of lattice structure performance before their physical realization. Consequently, the research activity of Friuli Innovazione has been focused on FEA application to analyze lattice structure models in additive manufacturing.

This study aimed to develop lattice structure model and perform FEA using different unit cell, different sizes, different thickness and a constant volume.

The FEA simulation allows to evaluate the mechanical behaviour of the lattice structure before fabricating into a real part.

The material used for the simulation was the 316 stainless steel.

First step: software selection and training

Lattice-generating software and lattice features in the CAD software are the only way to create lattice structures.

There's a wide range of sophistications and features among the software options so we compared several solutions.

Among these Autodesk Fusion 360, BASF Ultrasim Lattice Engine, Sulis and NTopology.

Latticing tools within the standard Fusion 360 are quite useful. It's possible to vary the lattice's cells gradually along a direction, and, unlike most programs that involve hollowing out a part and adding a lattice, lets its users design a part inside out. This software allows to create a lattice and then form a skin over it, letting the lattice cell structure shrink as it nears the skin, producing a cell structure that effectively distributes local stresses from the surface to the internal lattice.

BASF Ultrasim 3D Lattice Engine, aims to take the math out of lattices and make it easier to explore different lattice geometries and implement them into product design cycles faster with a click-and-apply approach. Powered by Hyperganic, the Munich-based algorithmic engineering software company, Ultrasim 3D Lattice Engine offers users a wide array of lattice patterns, each of which has been tested and validated for different application groups.

Sulis is used to create complex lattice structures and fluid flow channels for use across a range of industries, including aerospace, automotive, medical, and industrial machinery. It's a 3D printing design software tool featuring an implicit modelling kernel tailored specifically to latticing and a one-click lattice creation feature, Sulis enables to add lightweight structures to models and fine-tune their properties.

The final choice has been NTopology.

In this software new field-driven design enables engineers to use simulation results as design parameters to control the designs.

nTop offers a deep variety of lattice options and features that make it faster than a lot of CAD programs. Because the software is based on implicit modelling, where 3D geometry is defined as a mathematical function, not as external surfaces and edges, engineers can quickly generate complex structures – like lattices – while providing the reliability needed to feed automated design loops.

The latticing features included with nTop are extremely powerful and offer almost complete control over every aspect of the lattice structure, including the ability to define your own unit cell.

Because Ntopology uses field-based design and therefore it is completely different from traditional CAD the training was a bit complex and took longer than expected.

Second step: lattice structures generation

Through control of various [parameters lattice](#) structures can produce unique mechanical, electrical, thermal and acoustic properties.

The aims of our research are the optimization of lattice structure design from the mechanical point of view by changing the size of unit cell or the thickness of the beams at a constant volume and the comparison among different lattice structures. In literature has been observed that the changes in unit cell affects the strength of lattice structure, posing a challenge for additive manufacturing.

As already mentioned, some lattices have the same repeating unit cell throughout the entire part. These are known as periodic lattices. The alternative to this is where the cells are connected randomly throughout the global structure. These are called stochastic lattice structures.

Stochastic lattices are commonly used in biomedical applications since they can be designed to closely resemble the properties of human bone and are excellent at reconnecting bone structures inside the body.

The problem of using stochastic structures concerns the need to have oversize the product during design. This is necessary because the present irregularities could create micro-zones of weakening caused by defects or geometries not complying.

The choice to use highly oriented materials is therefore due both to their greater specific resistance, compared to stochastic cellular materials, than to greater reliability.

For these reasons in our activities we have considered periodic lattice only.

We designed the first models foreseeing the use of Laser Powder bed fusion (LPBF) technology for the subsequent prototyping and 316 stainless steel as the material. In the second phase of the research, we're going to use FDM and SLS printers to test polymers too.

As structures we used the TPMS lattices and the Strut lattices because they are the most performing from a mechanical point of view

We designed cubes of homogeneous size (20X20X20mm) with different lattice structures in terms of geometry, size of the unit cells and thickness of the beams.

Figure 1: Fluorite and Gyroid unit cells

Unit cell	Cell size	Thickness
Fluorite	From 5x5x5mm to 10x10x10mm	From 0,5mm to 0,8mm
Iso Truss	From 5x5x5mm to 10x10x10mm	From 0,5mm to 0,8mm
Gyroid (TPMS)	From 5x5x5mm to 10x10x10mm	From 0,5mm to 0,8mm

Third step: FEA Analysis

There are three main methods for simulating lattices in nTopology: Solid Elements, Beam Elements and Homogenization.

- Solid Elements are volumetric finite element mesh of the entire lattice structure.
- Beam Elements are finite element nodes along lattice vertices connected by lattice beams. This method greatly reduces the number of elements from a typical volume mesh but ignores certain mechanical behaviour like edge effects and stress concentrations in the lattice.
- Homogenization is a Solid FEA simulation on a single unit cell of the lattice

Solid elements considers edge effects, allows to locatable maximum stress point, is precise and applicable to Beams and TPMS: for these reasons we preferred this method.

To evaluate these effects, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was conducted by applying static loading at one end of the surface manufacturing.

In this phase we simulated the deformation of the models at a static load of 5000 Newton (approximately 1 N= 0,10197 Kg)

Figure 2: Simulation

Stress simulations, especially those using a finite element approach, can be very computationally intensive when large lattice structures are involved. Most approaches involve extrapolating the properties of the unit cell across the entire structure, but if the cell types and sizes vary significantly, then physical testing may be the only way to accurately evaluate the performance of very large and complex lattice designs.

The results of this first simulation is that gyroid TPMS structures have greater resistance to compression loads compared to fluorite and Iso Truss with the same thickness and cells dimension.

Increasing cell size reduces the ability to resist compression.

The fluorite-type lattice structures deform less than Iso truss in the case of cells with dimensions of 5x5x5mm and beam thickness of 0.5mm but the Iso Truss ones have better performance with 10 mm cells or with 0.8 mm beams.

Next steps: from virtual to real and design of new lattice structures

The next phase will consist of printing the physical models and carrying out the traditional mechanical tests to verify any differences in results compared to the simulation.

The simulation will also be extended to polymeric materials.

New lattice structures will be designed and tested.